

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: ADEDOKUN****FIRST NAME: OLUWASANMI****PROGRAM CODE: DIPH****COURSE CODE: ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 1****INSTRUCTOR: DR GULMA****Edit or delete text to show the basic information below:**

The author applied UK conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics

The student must use Turabian/Chicago parenthetical/in-text references (ideally with Zotero) and confirm below:

The author did use Zotero to insert references

The author did use Grammarly Premium (provided by EUCLID)

My plagiarism rate (per Grammarly Premium) is: 1%

The author used the following software: (MS Office 365 on Windows11)

List your six key concepts with the page number in the text (then bold these terms in your RP) (samples below):

1. Essay Writing (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2021a, 6–14)
2. Punctuations (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2021a, 15–23)
3. American vs. British English (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2021a, 24–32)
4. Plagiarism (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2021a, 33–39)
5. Style Guide (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2021a, 40–57)
6. Latin Abbreviations and Expressions (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2021a, 58–64)

SCHOLARLY ESSAY WRITING

1) INTRODUCTION

The ACA-401/ACA-401D coursepack (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2021a) has been designed as an essential companion to any would-be scholar like me. It articulates the ‘dos’ and ‘don’ts’ of scholarly writing in an easy-to-read format covering such topics as 1) Essay writing, 2) Punctuations, 3) American vs. British English, 4) Plagiarism, 5) Style guide, and 6) Latin abbreviations and expressions. The last chapter on ‘Sample Corrections to Papers’ gives the reader a practical understanding of the application of the course content.

In reading through the material, there were many ‘light-bulb’ moments for me as I came to understand that I had committed many blunders in many of my previous writings, not having had the privilege of such training in the past. Here, I present my gleanings from the reading material during a few of those ‘moments of illumination’.

2) **ESSAY WRITING**

‘Academic essay or scholarly writing is nonfictional writing produced as part of academic work’ (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2021a, 7). It includes documentation of research findings, monographs, conference papers, books, literature reviews, explication, technical reports, translations, or student presentations [undergraduate or postgraduate]. The writings may or may not be published in journals, books, newspapers, or periodicals or retained as manuscripts, theses, or dissertations (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2021a, 7). Essentially, academic essays seek to provide the answer(s) to a hypothesis based on evidence (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2021a, 7).

There are critical steps in academic essay writing, though not following a rigid order, but are necessary to have a coherent essay. The importance of starting early to read and carry out further research into the subject matter cannot be over-emphasized. This ensures that the writer has ample time to distill ideas and logically present them when writing and prevents the errors associated with writing in a hurry. It is also essential to develop a plan for how to write at the initial stages. The plan provides an initial sketchy overview of what to write, which may be refined further as one gets more insight from researching the topic. As one explores the topic, taking notes summarizing what is already known, gaps in knowledge requiring further research, and sifting through to identify relevant and irrelevant materials to the subject matter is essential. Before writing, it is necessary to organize your ideas by clearly articulating the questions to be answered, the order in which to present ideas, and identifying relevant evidence to support your arguments. A first draft of the essay is produced, consisting of the introduction, the body of the paper, and the conclusion. Usually, the essay's body is written first, comprising paragraphs that present specific ideas and provide evidence to support your point of view and, if possible, refute opposing points of view. The introduction provides a general overview of what your essay is about in its opening statements and narrows down to specifics of the question you wish to answer [a thesis statement] (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2021a, 10) is then written. Lastly, you write the conclusion, which restates your thesis question and branches out by providing a summary of your answer to the question and the broad implications of your submissions for future practice and research. The conclusion should not introduce any new concepts not previously discussed in the essay (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2021a, 16).

A scientific or scholarly essay is incomplete without proper referencing of the sources of evidence used to back up your submissions. It ensures that you give due credit to the previous researchers who generated the evidence you are using. One must understand the proper referencing style acceptable to the recipient of your essay, be it a school faculty or journal, and adhere closely to it throughout the essay. Lastly, making time to review and edit your writing, usually after taking a short break to reflect on your initial draft to get fresh perspectives or acquire new insights from additional research, will help to improve the quality of your final output. Before submitting your work, review the requirements again to ascertain compliance with the submission guidelines and timelines.

3) PUNCTUATIONS

Correct punctuations ensure that you convey to your readers your actual intent and do not misrepresent your thoughts. A thorough understanding of punctuation marks and their proper uses is essential to correctly communicating your thoughts without distorting the meaning of your sentences (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2021a, 16). Punctuation marks include:

- Apostrophe - used to indicate possession or to indicate that letters have been omitted when two words are combined (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2021a, 16–17).
- Comma - used between items in a list or before and after a clause that may be removed from a sentence without altering the meaning of the sentence, that is, a non-defining clause. It may also be used between multiple qualitative adjectives, which can be modified with comparatives such as ‘very’, ‘quite’, and so on (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2021a, 19–20).
- Colon - used to introduce a subclause that depends on the main clause before it for clarity (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2021a, 18).
- Semicolon - used to link two related but otherwise complete sentences. It can also be used in a complicated sentence to make the sentence clearer (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2021a, 18).
- Bullets points - used to itemize lists (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2021a, 18).
- Brackets - used like a pair of dashes or commas to provide extra information on a preceding non-defining phrase (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2021a, 17).
- Dashes - may be interchanged with brackets or commas to provide extra information in a non-defining phrase; used to link two parts of a sentence; used to link ranges of numbers or concepts; used to connect names of joint authors or creators; or used in place of a colon (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2021a, 20).
- Hyphens - used either in adjectival phrases preceding a noun or including a verb particle. It may also be used in repeated prefixes; in prefixes preceding a proper name, number, or date; in geographical compass points; and in spelt-out numbers (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2021a, 21).
- Ellipsis - used to show that some text is missing from a quotation, to indicate a pause for comic effect in a sentence, or to indicate a trailing-off of speech or thought (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2021a, 22).
- Full stop, exclamation mark, and question mark - used at the end of sentences either to represent an end to the sentence, an imperative, or a question, respectively. Only one of the three is used in any sentence (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2021a, 22).
- Quotation marks - used to represent quoted speech. A single quotation mark is used to indicate a direct quotation, while a double quotation mark is used to indicate a quotation within a quotation. Single quotation marks may also be used to show titles that are part of a volume of publications (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2021a, 23).

4) AMERICAN VS. BRITISH ENGLISH

American English has grown steadily in international significance since World War II, parallel to the growth of U.S. political, economic, technological, and cultural influence worldwide. American English is currently the dominant influence on "world English" (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2021a, 25).

I can relate to the assertion in the epigraph above (Turabian et al. 2018, 330). Having been trained with the British curriculum and has worked with American organizations over the last fifteen years, my writing features a mix of the nuances of the two writing standards. Therefore, it is imperative that I take the content of this section seriously as I continue my scholarly journey towards a Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) at EUCLID University. Differences in Standard British English (SBE) and Standard American English (SAE) include words with different pronunciations but having the same meaning (e.g., laboratory, secretary, leisure), different spelling but with the same pronunciation (e.g., SBE "colour" vs. SAE "color"), same term but different spelling and pronunciation (e.g., SBE "Maths" vs. SAE "Math"), and same word but with different additional meaning (e.g., SBE "maize" vs. SAE "sweetcorn"). Other nuanced differences between British and American English may be related to grammar, syntax, punctuations, pluralization, data formats, use of honorifics [Titles], and jargon (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2021a, 25–32). I submit that grasping the breadth of the differences between SBE and SAE will require a lifetime of learning.

5) PLAGIARISM

‘Plagiarism is when the writer uses a source of information without giving credit to the author of that source of information’ (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2021a, 34).

Every writer must guard against plagiarism. All quotes, paraphrases, copying, or pasting from the internet of the work of others should be properly referenced. In addition, when using data or visuals borrowed from others, it should be appropriately referenced (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2021a, 34–35; Turabian et al. 2018, 326). Information that is commonly known need not be referenced (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2021a, 37). The method used to indicate the source of a piece of information is referred to as citing and is done in two ways; 1) In-text citations as footnotes or endnotes, 2) A list of works cited called bibliography or reference list (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2021a, 34–39).

In-text citations may be either footnotes or endnotes. Footnotes are usually numeric superscript notations in the text, and the details are provided at the bottom of the page on which they are cited. In-text citations for Endnotes, however, may be numbers enclosed in and, in some instances, Page numbers (depending on the referencing style employed). The Turabian referencing style is the preferred referencing style by Euclid University. It must include the author’s Last name, Year of publication, and page numbers (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2021b, 1). A list of works cited is also referred to as a bibliography or reference list. This a listing of the detailed references cited in the essay providing sufficient detail for

the reader to find the referenced documents (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2021a, 52). Reference lists follow strict formatting rules, depending on whether the citations are for journal articles, newspaper articles, books, book chapters, reports, or internet websites.

Direct quotes from a source document should be done sparingly; however, when using direct quotes from a source, the source document should be cited appropriately (Turabian et al. 2018, 326). For running quotes [short quotes], quotation marks should be provided at the beginning and end of the quotes, while longer quotes, usually one hundred words or more in length or running into more than four lines (Gibaldi and Modern Language Association of America 2009, 93; Turabian et al. 2018, 327, 328) should be inserted as a blockquote and indented. In this case, quotation marks are not required. 'It is impossible to overemphasize the importance of meticulous accuracy in quoting from the works of others' (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2021a, 48). On the other hand, when paraphrasing an original work, the paraphrase must be worded differently from the original work. Still, the information provided must accurately represent the author's initial thoughts (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2021a, 36).

6) STYLE GUIDE

A style guide documents the approach to some aspects of writing style that promote consistency in the writing style, even when there are multiple contributors to a document. While there are many authoritative sources on style for written English, creating room for a healthy debate on elements of style, a good writer should always consider the acceptable style to their readers and seek to adhere to such kind to increase acceptance (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2021a, 41–42).

The Chicago Manual of Style provides standard recommendations for using abbreviations, capitalization, compound words, italics, quotation marks, numbers, and quotations in essay writing (be it technical, business, journalism, or web copywriting). The guide also sets standards for page formatting, footnotes, endnotes, bibliographies, headings, listings, and formatting tables. 'Turabian's Manual for Writers is the official guide to applying Chicago style to "term papers, theses, and dissertations," that is, final manuscripts' (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2021a, 50).

7) LATIN ABBREVIATIONS AND EXPRESSIONS

Even though the use of Latin abbreviations and expressions is not encouraged in technical writing to avoid readers' misinterpretations (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2021a, 59), the role of Latin abbreviations and expressions in writing is worth mentioning. Latin abbreviations are more appropriate in footnotes, bibliographies, and informal writing, but a good understanding of the standard abbreviations and expressions will guard against misuse. EUCLID recommends that,

It is best to create content using "plain language" principles. Plain language (also called plain English) is a writing style that is simple and direct but not simplistic or patronizing.

When writing in plain language, use short sentences with simple words. Avoid jargon, acronyms, and abbreviations (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2021a, 59).

8) CONCLUSION

In this first response paper (RP1), I have summarized insights gained from the EUCLID ACA-401/ACA-401D course pack with respect to writing scholarly essays. I have learnt lessons relating to planning and organizing my essay writing; using correct punctuations to ensure my intended meanings are retained; being consistent in the use of standard American or British English; correctly referencing the sources of my evidence; applying a consistent style guide; and the role, and common usage of Latin abbreviations and expressions. This reading material will remain a reference document not only through the period of my PhD pursuit but throughout my scholarly writing career as I strive to become accustomed to its dictates.

REFERENCES

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